

A Study on Financial Performance of Tancem at Ariyalur Unit

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Abstract

This study examines the Financial Performance and relationship between profitability and Working Capital Management of Tamilnadu Cement Corporation Limited (TANCEM) Ariyalur unit in Tamilnadu. The main aims of the thesis are as follows: To evaluate the Financial Performance of the TANCEM parent body with TANCEM Ariyalur unit. To examine the relationship between Working Capital Management and Profitability of TANCEM parent body and TANCEM unit at Ariyalur unit. To evaluates the operating efficiency of the TANCEM parent body and TANCEM unit at Ariyalur.

Sampling Procedure, Design and methodology: *This research work is a quantitative analysis and the researcher applied two methods: Firstly, the researcher used correlation models, specifically Pearson correlation to measure the degree of association between different variables under consideration. Secondly, the researcher used Regression analysis to estimate the causal relationships between profitability variable, liquidity and other chosen variables. The research design of the study is "Correlation and Regression Analysis". The following methods of analysis are used in the study: (i) Ratio Analysis, (ii) Comparative Financial Statements, (iii) Common size Financial Statements and (iv) Schedule of changes in Working Capital Management. The study is based on Secondary data. The annual reports of TANCEM constituted the single most important source of data.*

Introduction

One of the most important elements of success in Business is Finance. It has rightly been said that business needs 'money' to make more money. However, it is also true that money gets more money, only when it is properly managed. Hence, efficient management of every business enterprise is closely linked with efficient management of finance. Business Finance usually deals with financial planning, acquisition of funds, allocation of funds and financial control. J.Fred Weston states, "Traditionally, the literature of Business Finance has emphasised either the management of working capital or the acquisition of funds."¹ Financing is the process of organizing the flow of funds so that a business can carry out its business activities in the most efficient manner and meet its obligations in due time. As Irwin Friend writes, "A firm's success and even survival, its ability and willingness to maintain production and to invest in fixed and working capital are to a very extent considerably determined by its financial policies both past and present"²

Statement of the Problem

In TANCEM the production on large quantity of inventory which is a part of working capital, with the sale in large volumes and mostly on credit to Government Departments, some part of the receivable are received in next year or shift into next year which impact on yearly firm's profitability. This could have significant impact on TANCEM profitability.

The researcher reviewed existing literature and gone through the problems of Cement manufacturing industries in general and State Government owned TANCEM in particular seeking clarification to the following specific problems:

1. Whether the TANCEM has operating efficiency or not?
2. What is the status of performance of TANCEM?
3. Whether the TANCEM and TANCEM Ariyalur unit perform remarkably or not?
4. Is there any impact of Working Capital Management on Profitability of TANCEM?
5. What is the contribution and impact of TANCEM Ariyalur unit in the parent TANCEM.

To address the above issues, the present study namely, "A study on Financial Performance of TANCEM Ariyalur unit in Tamilnadu" has been taken up. It is a maiden attempt to analyze the financial performance and the relationship between Working Capital Management and profitability of the Public Sector undertakings i.e. TANCEM Ariyalur unit.

Scope of the Study

With regard to financial performance analysis of TANCEM, the researcher has taken up Financial Performance analysis and Working capital management alone. In the case of Financial Performance analysis the researcher mainly concentrated on ratio analysis. The other aspects are not focused much. In case of Working Capital Management analysis the schedule of changes in Working Capital and working capital regression model and beta analysis alone taken into considerations. Further in the case of Working Capital Management there in no detailed analyses of Receivable Management, Cash Management and Inventory Management are carried out. TANCEM has two cement plants, the first one situated in Alangulam in Virudhunagar District and second one in Ariyalur at Ariyalur District. Apart from the two cement plants TANCEM also has one Asbestos Sheet Plants at Alangulam and another Stoneware Pipes Plants at Vridhachalam, Cuddalore District. The study of the Financial Performance of TANCEM is conducted in Ariyalur unit in Ariyalur District and TANCEM parent body in Chennai. The other units namely Alangulam Asbestos Sheet Plant at Alangulam and Stoneware Pipes plant at Virudhachalam does not included in the study.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are indicated below

1. To understand the Origin and Growth of Cement Industry in General and of TANCEM in particular.
2. To evaluate the Financial Performance of the TANCEM parent body with TANCEM Ariyalur unit.
3. To examine the relationship between Working Capital Management and Profitability of TANCEM parent body and TANCEM unit at Ariyalur unit.
4. To evaluate the operating efficiency of the TANCEM parent body and TANCEM unit at Ariyalur.
5. To offer remedial measures to improve the profitability of TANCEM and TANCEM unit at Ariyalur through the effective management of working capital and improvement of financial performance.

Hypotheses Testing

The purpose of this study is to find out the relationship between profitability and working capital management, the study makes a set of testable hypothesis {the Null Hypothesis H₀ versus Alternative Hypothesis H₁}.

The First Hypothesis of this study is as follows

1. **H₀₁:** There is no Correlation between Working Capital Management and Profitability of the TANCEM unit at Ariyalur.
2. **H₁₁:** There is a positive Correlation between Working Capital Management and profitability of TANCEM unit at Ariyalur.

Second Hypothesis of the study is as follow

1. **H₀₂:** There is no association between Liquidity and Profitability of the TANCEM parent body and TANCEM unit at Ariyalur.
2. **H₁₂:** There exists negative relationship between Liquidity and Profitability of the TANCEM parent body and TANCEM unit at Ariyalur.

Third Hypothesis of the study is as follow

1. **H₀₄:** There is no relationship between Debt and Profitability of TANCEM parent body and TANCEM unit at Ariyalur.
2. **H₁₄:** There is a negative relationship between Debt and Profitability of TANCEM parent body and TANCEM unit at Ariyalur.

Area and Period of the Study

The period of the study with regard to the Secondary Data covers to 13 financial years from 2000-2001 to 2012-2013. The study area is confined to the TANCEM parent body at Chennai, Tamilnadu and TANCEM unit at Ariyalur, Ariyalur District.

TANCEM ARIYALUR UNIT

TANCEM CHENNAI HEAD OFFICE

VIRUDHNAGAR ALANGULAM ASBESTOS AND PIPE UNIT

Chart 1.1 Map Showing the Study Area

Methodology

Research Question: Does the change in working capital impacts on the firm's profitability of TANCEM?

Research Approach: In quantitative analysis we applied two methods: First: we used correlation models, specifically Pearson correlation to measure the degree of association between different variables under consideration. Second: we used Regression analysis to estimate the causal relationships between profitability variable, liquidity and other chosen variables. This research study is focused on the quantitative approach, whereas the quantitative approach illustrate by name itself that it is based on objective realities. This approach is considered measurable one in terms of physical quantity and in facts and figures.

Research Design: The research design is the procedural details of the study by which data is collected which aims to develop the set of methods and procedures, which help to test the research question, and with a degree of confidence, research design of my study is focused on 'Regression Analysis'

Research Tools: The analysis and interpretation of financial statements is used to determine the financial position and results of operations as well. A number of methods or devices are used to study the relationship between different statements. An effort is made to use those devices which clearly analyze the position of the enterprise. The following methods of analysis are used in the study:

- Ratio Analysis
- Comparative Financial Statements
- Common size Financial Statements
- Changes in Working Capital Management

Data Source: The study is based on Secondary Data. The Annual Reports of the Company constituted the single most important source of data. It includes the related data of the Annual Reports of TANCEM parent body and TANCEM Ariyalur in different time period from 2000-2001 to 2011-13. The researcher obtained the relevant data from the Finance Department in the Ariyalur, Tiruchirappalli District and the TANCEM parent body through the web sites. The accounting information reported in the financial statements is rearranged in a form suitable for analysis. Additional information is obtained from books, business dailies and magazines, Libraries and web sites.

Statistics / Multivariate technique: As far as concerned to this research study, the researcher want to evaluate the impact on relationship between the working capital management Profitability on selected sample time period. Whereas, researcher found correlation or Regression Analyses technique would be suitable for quantifying the effect of variables to each other on the basis of gathered data from the TANCEM.

Variables Used for Analysis of Data

This study undertakes the issue of identifying key variables that influence Working Capital Management of TANCEM. Choice of the variables is influenced by the previous studies on working capital management. All the variables stated below have been used to test the Hypotheses of our study.

Net Operating Profitability (NOP) which is a measure of Profitability of the firm is used as dependant variable. It is defined as Operating Income plus depreciation, and divided by total assets minus financial assets.

Average Collection Period (ACP) used as proxy for the Collection Policy is an independent variable. It is calculated by dividing account receivable by sales and multiplying the result by 365 (number of days in a year).

Inventory Turnover in Days (ITID) used as proxy for the Inventory Policy is also an independent variable. It is calculated by dividing inventory by cost of goods sold and multiplying with 365 days. Average Payment Period (APP) used as proxy for the Payment Policy is also an independent variable. It is calculated by dividing accounts payable by purchases and multiplying the result by 365.

Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) used as a comprehensive measure of working capital management is another independent variable, and is measured by adding Average Collection Period with Inventory Turnover in Days and deducting Average Payment Period.

Current Ratio (CR) which is a traditional measure of liquidity is calculated by dividing current assets by current liabilities.

Debit Ratio (DR) which is measured through total debt divided by total asset

Income to Sale Ratio (ISR) which is measure operating income plus depreciation amount of the year and the divided by sale through out the year.

Income to Total Assets (IA) it is measured operating income plus depreciation amount and then divided by total asset.

Sales Growth (SGROW) is calculated by current sale year minus previous year sale and then divided by previous year sale.

The general form of the model is:

$$NOP = \beta_1 (ACP) + \beta_2 (CCC) + \beta_3 (APP) + \beta_4 (CR) + \beta_5 (ITID) + \beta_6 (DR) + \beta_7 (IS) + \beta_8 (IA) + \beta_9 (SGROW) + \varepsilon$$
 Where,

1. ACP = Average Collection Period in Days
2. CCC = Cash Conversion Cycle in Days
3. ITID = Inventory Turnover in Days
4. CR = Current Ratio
5. DR = Debt Ratio
6. IS = Income to Sale Ratio
7. IA = Income to Total Asset
8. SGROW = Sales Growth

1.9 Limitations of the Study

The study is based on secondary data collected from TANCEM, therefore the quality of the study depends purely upon the accuracy, reliability and quality of the secondary data source. Approximation and relative measures with respect to the data source might impact the results.

First hand information from the Company regarding the financial plan, method of controlling the debts, management of cash and other vital details are important for the analysis of working capital but the Finance Department reluctant to provide the necessary data in time. Hence, the researcher unable to conduct the detailed analysis of Cash management, receivable management

and inventory management. However the researcher collected financial statements by making necessary enquiry with the finance department personnel for conducting the working capital and financial statement analysis.

Further, the inherent limitations of financial statements and ratios are also be reflected in the study. Due to time and cost constraints, the study is confined to thirteen years data only, i. e. from 2001–2013. Therefore, a detailed analysis covering a lengthy period, which may give slightly different results. The study is based on data given by TANCEM Ariyalur unit, Tamilnadu. Therefore, the accuracy of results is purely based on the data supplied by the TANCEM.

Comparison of Production, Capacity Utilization, Sales Profit/Loss and Net increase or Decrease in Working Capital

Table 5.36 it is concluded that whenever there is increase in working capital the capacity as well as production of the study unit increased and profit volume also increased except during the year 2003-04. During the years 2004, 2006, 2010 and 2011 there were application of funds and management of Ariyalur unit effectively manage the working capital and enable to increase the profit volume.

Beta Analysis: It is found from the chart 5.36.1 that, changes in working capital fluctuates as years pass the above to change is understood with the help of Beta for this ratio over 12 years is 97.75%. It means there is 100% change in working capital. The working capital is changing 511.41%. This is explained by 99.67% of the data under observation.

Relationship between independent variables and Net Operating Profit

Multiple regression analysis was applied to find the relationship between independent variables towards net operating profit to identify the best predictor from them. The following results were arrived at and are shown in this table 5.39.

The value of $R(0.997)$ is the correlation of the nine independent variables Average Collection Period in Days(X_1), Cash Conversion Cycle in Days(X_2), Average Payment Period(X_3), Current Ratio(X_4), Inventory Turnover in Days(X_5), Debt Ratio(X_6), Income to Sales Ratio(X_7), Income to Total Asset(X_8), Sales Growth(X_9) with the dependent variable Net Operating Profit (Y). The inter-correlations among the nine independent variables are taken into account. The R-square (0.995), which indicates all independent variables together explains 99.5% of the variance in net operating profit, which is highly significant ($F=41.798$, $p<0.05$).

Hypotheses Testing

It is concluded from the hypotheses testing that 1. There is a positive Correlation between Working Capital Management and profitability of TANCEM unit at Ariyalur. 2. There exists negative relationship between Liquidity and Profitability of the TANCEM Chennai and TANCEM at Ariyalur. 3. There is a negative relationship between Debt and Profitability of TANCEM Chennai and TANCEM at Ariyalur.

SWOT Analysis

It reveals that the weaknesses of the TANCEM are more than the Opportunities and Threats. The weaknesses may be cleared or removed with efficient management of working capital through reducing the debt-equity ratio and reduction of raw-material cost, input cost and sincere attempt on receivable management. Hence, it is concluded that the effective management of working capital will reduce the weaknesses of the TANCEM and thereby increase the strength. This aptly match the study conducted and concluded by the Tiwari R.S.(1998) that “proper management, effective controls and cost reduction strategies are the most important methods to improve the profitability in cement factories.”

Conclusion

From this analysis the researcher concludes that the financial performance of TANCEM Ariyalur Unit is very impressive when compared to the TANCEM parent Body. The operating efficiency of TANCEM Ariyalur unit is satisfactory. The TANCEM Ariyalur unit sustained losses only two years and rest of the years under the study gaining profit. The impact of Ariyalur unit in the TANCEM performance is impressive. Due to earning of the Ariyalur unit the parent body enables to reduce its losses. There is a proper working capital management in Ariyalur Unit and in this regard the researcher very much appreciates the Finance Department of the Ariyalur. Finally, there is an impact of TANCEM Ariyalur unit on TANCEM Chennai performance is vital and visible from the study.

Suggestions

The following suggestions were given for the betterment of the financial position of the TANCEM Chennai and Ariyalur Unit.

Recommendation to TANCEM CHENNAI

1. In the case of TANCEM Chennai working capital turnover ratio was increasing year by year except in 2012. Increasing rate usually indicates relative inefficiency in the use of capital from the profit view point. It may also show that management is protecting the capital for business. It evident that the share capital of TANCEM not fluctuating and remaining for constant for more than 12 years. Hence, the working capital turnover may be reduced by efficiently utilizing the capital in the business.
2. TANCEM under the constraints to improve the operating efficiency otherwise it will affect the survival of TANCEM. Hence, the researcher suggested that TANCEM parent body may take necessary steps to reduce the cost of raw-materials, power and fuel cost, packing charges and other expenses. TANCEM also finding out the alternative source of power supply i.e. solar energy.
3. TANCEM's capital resources being stretched too far and indicates overtrading and resulting in paucity of funds in TANCEM. Therefore, it needs more funds for working capital. Further there is a need to raise borrowings so that funds may be infused to TANCEM Ariyalur unit. Therefore, TANCEM may be infusing more share capital because it is more or less constant over the years.
4. TANCEM Chennai should take necessary steps to collect the sundry debtors particularly collect receivable from other Government departments that will increase its Net Profit and improve the Debt-Equity ratio.
5. TANCEM Chennai may take necessary steps to setup the stoneware pipes and asbestos products and backward integration to increase the profitability of the TANCEM.
6. The Government takes further step to argument the production by the way of making technological advancement in production and distribution of cement and install additional modern cement plant in Ariyalur unit as it is very essential and viable in its operations.
7. The TANCEM Chennai allocates further funds to Ariyalur unit to increase the fixed assets and to increase the liquidity position TANCEM parent body.
8. The TANCEM Chennai may reduce the administrative delay in sanctioning the necessary funds to Ariyalur unit.
9. The debt-equity ratio was not up to the mark in TANCEM parent body and it may be improved.

10. The TANCEM may approach the apex body namely Tamilnadu State Government to increase budgetary allocation for increase of the capacity of the Ariyalur unit as it utilizes 100% capacity many a times during the study period.

Recommendation to TANCEM ARIYALUR UNIT

1. Even though the sales volume has been increased in Ariyalur unit but the Tamil Nadu Government has not been taken any step to commission any new plant in the Ariyalur unit during the 12 years study periods. Hence, the Government of Tamilnadu may take serious steps to commissioning new plant in Ariyalur unit.
2. TANCEM ARIYALUR UNIT has maintained cash and bank balances at the lowest level in the recent years therefore, it may take further steps to make adequate cash and bank balances to improve the liquidity positions.
3. TANCEM ARIYALUR UNIT may take measures to clear the inventory level or take efforts to increasing the sales.
4. TANCEM ARIYALUR UNIT should try to increase the Fixed Assets, so that it will improve the fixed assets turnover ratio.
5. The net working capital of Ariyalur unit has been oscillating and it may take steps to increase Working capital.
6. It should take necessary steps to reduce power and fuel cost because it is nearly 50 percentage of sales value. It may send proposal to TANCEM parent body as well as the Tamilnadu State Government for installing alternative sources of power supply i.e. Air Wind or Solar energy.
7. Ariyalur unit has not collected the sundry debtors in time and there was no proper provisioning in the Balance Sheet. It must give much attention to make collection of debtors and make provisioning then and there to write off the bad debts.

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